

Gibbs' Paradox, Indistinguishability and Local Pressure

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Gibbs' paradox is often said to be solved by considering particles in a gas to be indistinguishable, i.e. by using $N!$ in calculations. Furthermore, this indistinguishability is said to ultimately follow from quantum mechanics. In particular, Gibbs' paradox is linked with the example of a container with two equal volume and temperature chambers with N particles of either the same or a different gas in each. The wall separating the two is lifted and a consideration made of the change (if any) in entropy. If the gases are the same, indistinguishability, i.e. $N!$ Or $(2N)!$, is required to make the entropies of the two chambers add to that of the system with the wall separating chambers removed.

It seems that the calculation of entropy in the above calculation is based on properties of the single particles. Classically, these properties are position and momentum and one consider various possible states based on these properties. It then becomes somewhat ambiguous whether one should treat the particles as distinguishable or indistinguishable. Using indistinguishability leads to an expression for entropy which is additive if the gases on each side of the container are the same, while distinguishability doesn't.

Here we try to formulate the problem in terms of pressure balance, in keeping with balance notions in Newtonian mechanics. In such a case, pressure is affected by spatial density and the distribution $f(\text{absolute}(p))$ where p is momentum. Instead of worrying about any particle property, we focus on what is necessary for a pressure balance and consider the lifting of the partition problem and indistinguishability in that light. In such a case, with the same gas on each side of a partition, the presence or absence of a partition does not affect pressure balance, even though microscopically a single particle once confined to half of the volume may now move throughout the full volume. The question we ask is whether this change in a microscopic constraint has anything to do with pressure balance. This question becomes perhaps more relevant when one considers the question in (1), namely why does the entropy of mixing increase when two different particles exist in each gas chamber and not when they are the same gas. A second question is what would happen if one thought the gases in the chambers were the same and some measurement later determined them to be slightly different. We argue that it is a pressure balance and not necessarily any property of a gas particle which is key. Thus, gas particles which are physically different in some respect, may be identical in terms of how they convert e (energy) into velocity and p momentum, the key components of pressure. For example, classically a gas of red billiard balls should yield the same result as one with green. One may develop a kind of information entropy based on colour, but it has nothing to do with pressure and the Maxwell-Boltzmann energy distribution.

Information Entropy

Shannon's entropy

$$S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

is an informational entropy. That is to say it is linked to a lack of knowledge about property i , expressed by the probability $P(i)$. The Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy may be expressed in the form of ((1)), i.e.

$$S \text{ (MB)} = - \sum_{ei} P(ei) \ln(P(ei)) \quad \text{where } P(i) = C \exp(-ei/T) \quad ((2))$$

It should be noted, however, that a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas is one which comes into equilibrium. Given that particles collide, one would expect a pressure balance throughout based on Newtonian mechanical force balance. As a result, spatial density and $P(ei)$ adjust to create this pressure balance,

in some manner. Properties or features of a gas particle which are not linked with pressure/energy may not be relevant to this pressure balance equilibrium even though there may be some kind of informational entropy associated with them.

We consider two examples. First, one may have a classical gas of red coloured particles and a different one with green coloured ones. The colour of a classical particle has nothing to do with its energy distribution, spatial density or pressure that is created, yet it is a physical property which may be linked with some kind of probability and hence some kind of informational entropy. A second example, which is more relevant, is the position of the particle. What matters for pressure balance is spatial density (among other things), i.e. how many particles are in a tiny volume. It is not clear that there is necessarily any relevance to pressure balance if identical particles (in terms of the impulse hits they yield and how they use energy) are restricted to half a volume or a full volume.

Pressure Balance

As a result, we consider pressure balance of a gas broken into two equal volume chambers, each with N particles of the same type (in terms of how they convert energy to v velocity and p momentum, the key ingredients of pressure). Thus, there could be some properties which differ in the gases, but if these are not related to energy and pressure, they do not affect the problem and the gases are the same with respect to a pressure balance. If one lifts the barrier separating the two chambers, the same pressure balance equilibrium exists because it is thought of in terms of an energy distribution and a spatial density and neither of these change. The fact that a single particle, confined originally to one chamber, may now move throughout two has no effect on a pressure balance or the energy distribution.

If on the other hand, one has two gases with different energy / impulse responses, then lifting the barrier may lead to physical change because the physical pressure scenario now changes. Both chambers now have two different kinds of particles creating pressure and spatial density.

One may note that in the above argument, indistinguishability has a classical meaning (quantum mechanics is not needed). It means that each particle is associated with energy /velocity/ impulse in the same manner. From the point of view of pressure, it is irrelevant whether one particle or another imparts a specific impulse and has a fixed velocity, the two ingredients of pressure. As a result, indistinguishability may arise due to pressure balance considerations. In this way, there is no arbitrary consideration of whether a particle should be considered as distinguishable or not. Furthermore, this indistinguishability may be used in calculations, as is already well-known in the literature. We consider the case of two chambers with N particles of the same gas, i.e. the same in the sense of energy /impulse behaviour.

The expression for entropy for each chamber, using indistinguishability, is given by the \ln of the number of states:

$$\text{Chamber 1 or 2; } S = - \ln [\text{Sum over } e_i f(e_i) V / N!]^{\text{power } N} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{For the partition removed, one has: } S = - \ln [\text{Sum over } e_i f(e_i) 2V / (2N)!]^{\text{power } 2N} \quad ((4))$$

((4)) becomes, using Stirling's approximation: $\text{term} - 2N \ln(2V) + 2N \ln(2N)$, but the second term is: $-2N \ln(V)$ which is twice the term resulting from ((3)). Thus, with the $N!$, $(2N)!$ pressure balance based indistinguishability included, entropy ((2)) is twice the value of entropy ((3)), or entropy is additive if the gases are the same in terms of how a molecule reacts to energy/impulse.

If the gases are different, one has an expression ((3)) for each type of gas, but in ((4)), one uses the factor $(2N)! / N! N!$. Also one has to be careful in calculating $f(e_i)$ because some particles have structure and may rotate (like a dumbbell) etc. Such a particle does not respond to energy in the same way that a simple one does. Furthermore, for particles of different mass, the same energy represents different impulse hits and velocities, and hence pressure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may get into problems computing an information entropy or counting states. States are counted based on some kind of property. We argue, however, that not all properties are relevant to a physical pressure balance equilibrium, even if they have an associated probability. One is concerned with properties which are related to a balance in pressure. In such a case, one focuses on the number of particles in a tiny volume, i.e. spatial density, and energy distribution as well as how the particle associates its energy with velocity and p impulse (the two ingredients of pressure). If one has two chambers with N particles of the same gas (with respect to energy, impulse and speed) with the same temperature, removing the wall separating the chambers does not change the pressure balance, even though a single particle may move in $2V$ instead of V . Given that each particle converts energy e to v and p in the same manner, each particle is indistinguishable with respect to pressure. No use of quantum mechanics has been made to define this indistinguishability in this approach. An expression for entropy based on \ln (number of states) should then incorporate this indistinguishability which is one associated with pressure balance, we argue by using $N!$, $(2N)!$. If the gases are different in terms of how they convert e to v and p (e.g. dumbbell, different masses), then the physical pressure balance changes when one removes the wall.

References

1. Saunders, S. The Gibbs Paradox (Entropy, 2018)
[The Gibbs Paradox \(pitt.edu\)](#)